

THE GLOBAL OBESITY EPIDEMIC-PREVALENCE TRENDS AND PATHOPHYSIOLOGICAL MECHANISMS

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Abstract

Background: According to World Health Organization (WHO), adults with a Body Mass Index (BMI) ≥ 30 kg/m² are considered obese, while those with a BMI between 25 and 29.9 kg/m² are classified as overweight. Beyond lifestyle and behavioural factors, an intricate web of physiological mechanisms plays pivotal role in development and persistence of obesity. Understanding these mechanisms is essential for developing effective prevention and treatment strategies. **Aim:** To examine prevalence trends and pathophysiological mechanisms contributing to global obesity. **Methods:** A systematic search was conducted across major databases including PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science using predefined keywords related to obesity and human physiology. Studies published in English from 2000 to 2024 were included. Eligibility criteria focused on original research and high-quality reviews exploring physiological contributors to obesity in humans. The selection process followed PRISMA guidelines. **Key Findings:** This highlights the prevalence of obesity both globally and in India. It also identifies role of hormonal regulators such as leptin, ghrelin, insulin, and cortisol in appetite and energy metabolism. Neurophysiological centers, particularly hypothalamus, significantly influence hunger and satiety. Adipose tissue acts as an endocrine organ, releasing pro-inflammatory cytokines. Additionally, gut microbiota imbalances have been linked to altered nutrient absorption and metabolic dysfunction. Genetic and epigenetic factors further modulate these physiological pathways, contributing to individual susceptibility. **Conclusion:** Obesity is a complex, multifactorial condition deeply rooted in human physiology. Addressing its physiological foundations alongside lifestyle interventions may enhance effectiveness of treatment strategies and public health policies.

Keywords: Obesity, Hormones, Adipose Tissue, Prevalence.

INTRODUCTION

Obesity is defined as excessive or abnormal fat accumulation that may impair health. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), adults with a Body Mass Index (BMI) ≥ 30 kg/m² are considered obese, while those with a BMI between 25 and 29.9 kg/m² are classified as overweight¹. The Center for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) uses similar classification, categorizing obesity into three

classes, Class I (BMI 30–34.9), Class II (35–39.9), and Class III (≥ 40)². Obesity is recognized as a major public health concern, contributing to increased risks for type 2 diabetes, cardiovascular disease, certain cancers, and musculoskeletal disorders³. While diet and physical activity are critical factors in the development of obesity, mounting evidence suggests that physiological dysfunction plays a central role in energy imbalance and fat accumulation⁴. Dysregulation in appetite-controlling hormones, hypothalamic signaling, adipose tissue function, and metabolic pathways contributes to the complex etiology of obesity⁵. A better understanding of these internal mechanisms is crucial for designing targeted and sustainable interventions.

Aim

1. To study prevalence trends and pathophysiological mechanisms contributing to global obesity.

METHODOLOGY

This review was conducted following the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA 2020) guidelines to ensure methodological transparency. A comprehensive literature search was performed to identify relevant peer-reviewed studies exploring the physiological mechanisms and global prevalence of obesity. Databases Used were PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, Science Direct, Google Scholar.

Keywords and Boolean Operators: A predefined combination of Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) terms and free-text keywords was used. Boolean operators (AND, OR) were applied. Filters were applied for: Publication year (2000–2024); Language (English); Study types (Human studies only)

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Peer-reviewed original research and systematic reviews	Animal studies or in vitro research
Studies involving human subjects	Studies focused solely on surgical or pharmacological interventions without physiological insight
Focus on physiological mechanisms underlying obesity or global/regional prevalence	Editorials, letters, conference abstracts without full-text availability.
Published after January 2000	Non-English articles
Articles in English language	

Observations: Prevalence of Obesity Childhood obesity has soared tenfold from 0.7% to 6.9% in girls and from 0.9% to 9.3% in boys between 1975 and 2022. Globally, women exhibit higher obesity prevalence than men. In U.S., recent data (Aug 2021–2023) show 41.3% of women compared to 39.2% of men are obese⁶. Adult obesity rates have tripled globally since 1975. Specifically, obesity in men climbed from 4.8% in 1990 to 14.0% in 2022, and in women from 8.8% to 18.5%⁷.

Urban residents often have lower physical activity, greater consumption of high-energy processed diets compared to rural counterparts and thus more obesity⁸. Similar trends in the prevalence are observed even in India. A recent meta-analysis by Singh et al in 2024 identified that urban youth had 2.3 times higher risk of being obese compared to rural counterparts⁹.

Even a study by Indian Council of Medical Research published that 19.3% of Indian adolescents are either overweight or obese with urban areas bearing highest burden¹⁰. Some state specific studies in India like a 2023 cross sectional study in Kerala recorded 26.7% prevalence of obesity¹¹ and a study in Punjab among medical students showed 24.1% were obese and more than 30% showing signs of early insulin resistance and dyslipidemia¹².

These point out to epidemiological shift where obesity is becoming a precursor to metabolic syndrome warranting early screening interventions.

Underlying Physiological Mechanisms in Obesity:

Energy Balance and Metabolism: Obesity arises when energy intake chronically exceeds energy expenditure. The basal metabolic rate (BMR) accounts for approximately 60–75% of total energy expenditure and in obese individuals, although BMR may increase due to larger body mass, it does not proportionally compensate for excess caloric intake¹³. Another key component is thermogenesis, which involves heat production by brown adipose tissue and skeletal muscles in response to overfeeding or cold exposure¹⁴. This mechanism is often blunted in obese individuals, contributing to a reduced capacity to dissipate excess energy.

Hormonal Regulation: The interplay between multiple hormones intricately regulates appetite, satiety, and fat metabolism. Leptin, secreted by adipocytes signals satiety to hypothalamus; however, obese individuals often develop leptin resistance, where high circulating leptin levels fail to suppress appetite¹⁵. In contrast, ghrelin, secreted by stomach, stimulates hunger and rises before meals; its suppression is often inadequate in obesity, leading to increased food intake¹⁶. Insulin, primarily known for regulating blood glucose, also promotes fat storage and suppresses lipolysis. Hyperinsulinemia and insulin resistance are strongly associated with visceral fat accumulation¹⁷. Additionally, thyroid hormones like T3 and T4 regulate BMR, and even mild hypothyroidism can reduce energy expenditure and predispose individuals to weight gain¹⁸.

Central Nervous System and Hypothalamic Pathways: The hypothalamus, particularly arcuate nucleus, plays a central role in energy homeostasis by integrating hormonal and neuronal signals related to hunger and satiety¹⁹. Two distinct neuron populations—NPY/AgRP (orexigenic) and POMC/CART (anorexigenic)—regulate appetite in response to peripheral signals like leptin, insulin, and ghrelin. Disruption in this neural circuitry contributes significantly to obesity. Moreover, neurotransmitters such as dopamine and serotonin influencing eating. Dysregulation of these pathways can lead to compulsive overeating and preference for high-calorie, palatable foods²⁰.

Adipose Tissue as an Endocrine Organ: Adipose tissue is secreting various hormones and cytokines known as adipokines. White adipose tissue (WAT) stores energy and secretes adipokines, while brown adipose tissue (BAT) dissipates energy through thermogenesis²¹. In obesity, WAT becomes hypertrophic releasing pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α , IL-6 and resistin, which contribute to systemic insulin resistance and chronic inflammation²². Conversely, adiponectin, which enhances insulin sensitivity, is reduced in obese individuals, further exacerbating metabolic complications²³. The inflammatory state associated with dysfunctional adipose tissue is a key driver of obesity-related diseases like type 2 diabetes and atherosclerosis.

Gut Microbiota and Gut–Brain Axis: A diverse and balanced microbial ecosystem supports metabolic regulation, while dysbiosis—an imbalance in microbial composition—can lead to increased energy harvest from food, lipogenesis, and low-grade inflammation²⁴. Microbial metabolites like short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs), such as butyrate and acetate, influence gut hormones like GLP-1 and PYY, which modulate satiety and insulin secretion²⁵. Disruption in this gut–brain axis has been linked to increased appetite, reduced energy expenditure, and greater fat storage. The altered microbiome also affects intestinal permeability, facilitating systemic inflammation that contributes to metabolic dysfunction²⁶.

DISCUSSION

This systematic review highlights that obesity is not merely a consequence of excessive caloric intake but result of complex physiological regulation. While hormonal imbalances, hypothalamic signalling dysfunction, and adipose tissue inflammation underlie the biological propensity to gain weight²⁷, these internal drivers are amplified by modern lifestyle factors such as sedentary behaviour,

processed diets, and psychosocial stress^{27,28}. Thus, obesity must be viewed through a biopsychosocial lens, acknowledging the convergence of biological susceptibility and behavioural exposures²⁹.

Gaps in Current Knowledge and Research Inconsistencies: Despite advancements, several gaps remain in our understanding. For instance, while leptin resistance is well-documented, the exact molecular mechanisms behind impaired leptin signaling in obesity remain elusive⁵. Similarly, while gut dysbiosis is correlated with weight gain, causality versus association remains debated, and the translational potential of microbiota-based therapies is still under investigation²⁴.

CONCLUSION

Obesity is a multifactorial condition resulting from a complex interaction between biological, environmental, and behavioural factors. This review underscores that beyond caloric excess, physiological dysregulation plays a central role. Clinically, recognizing obesity as a disease with physiological complexity shifts focus from simplistic calorie-based interventions to more nuanced, individualized treatment plans. Given multidimensional nature of obesity, its prevention and management must be multidisciplinary.

References

- 1) WHO C Obesity: preventing and managing the global epidemic. World Health Organ Tech Rep Ser.2000 Jun 3;894(i-xii):1-253
- 2) Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. About Adult BMI | Healthy Weight, Nutrition, and Physical Activity [Internet]. Atlanta: CDC; 2023 [last accessed 2025 Jul 27]. Available from: <https://www.cdc.gov/bmi/adult-calculator/bmi-categories.html>
- 3) Ng, M., Fleming, T., Robinson, M., Thomson, B., Graetz, N., et al. (2014). Global obesity prevalence 1980–2013. *Lancet*, 384(9945), 766-781.
- 4) Bray, G. A., & Ryan, D. H. (2020). Update on obesity pharmacotherapy. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 1461(1), 1-15.
- 5) Hall KD, Farooqi IS, Friedman JM, Klein S, Loos RJF, Mangelsdorf DJ, O'Rahilly S, Ravussin E, Redman LM, Ryan DH, Speakman JR, Tobias DK. The energy balance model of obesity: beyond calories in, calories out. *Am J Clin Nutr*. 2022 May 1; 115(5):1243-1254. Doi: 10.1093/ajcn/nqac031. PMID: 35134825; PMCID: PMC9071483
- 6) Emmerich SD, Fryar CD, Stierman B, Ogden CL. Obesity and Severe Obesity Prevalence in Adults: United States, August 2021-August 2023. *NCHS Data Brief*. 2024 Sep; (508):10.15620/cdc/159281. doi: 10.15620/cdc/159281. PMID: 39808758; PMCID: PMC11744423.
- 7) Obesity Evidence Hub. Obesity trends in adults globally [Internet]. Cancer Council; [updated 2025; last accessed 2025 Jul 27]. Available from: <https://www.obesityevidencehub.org.au/collections/trends/adults-global>
- 8) Baruwa OJ, Gbadebo BM, Adeleye OJ, Tabana H, Fagbamigbe AF. Decomposing the rural-urban disparities in overweight and obesity among women of reproductive age in Nigeria. *BMC Womens Health*. 2023 Dec 21; 23(1):680. Doi: 10.1186/s12905-023-02813-2. PMID: 38129895; PMCID: PMC10734196.
- 9) Singh A, Thakur A, Yadav N, et al. Urban-rural disparities in overweight and obesity among Indian youth: A meta-analysis. *Indian J Pediatr*. 2024;91(2):110–117.
- 10) Anjana RM, Deepa M, Pradeepa R, et al. Prevalence of obesity and its metabolic consequences in young Indian adults: Results from the ICMR–INDIAB study. *Lancet Diabetes Endocrinol*. 2023;11(5):325–334.
- 11) Gopalakrishnan S, Thomas M, Rajeev A. Burden of obesity and associated metabolic risks among college students in coastal Kerala. *J Clin Diagn Res*. 2023;17(6): LE01–LE04.

- 12) Sharma R, Gill P, Bhatia A. Metabolic syndrome in medical students: An emerging concern in North India. *Int J Community Med Public Health*. 2024;11(1):101–106.
- 13) Hall, K. D., et al. (2012). Components of energy balance. *American Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, 95(4), 989-994.
- 14) Lowell, B. B., & Spiegelman, B. M. (2000). Molecular basis of adaptive thermogenesis. *Nature*, 404(6778), 652-660.
- 15) Ludwig DS, Friedman MI. Increasing adiposity: consequence or cause of overeating? *JAMA*. 2014 Jun 4;311(21):2167-8. doi: 10.1001/jama.2014.4133. Erratum in: *JAMA*. 2014 Jun 4;311(21):2168. PMID: 24839118.
- 16) Cummings DE, Overduin J. Gastrointestinal regulation of food intake. *J Clin Invest*. 2007 Jan;117(1):13-23. doi: 10.1172/JCI30227. PMID: 17200702; PMCID: PMC1716217.
- 17) Kahn SE, Hull RL, Utzschneider KM. Mechanisms linking obesity to insulin resistance and type 2 diabetes. *Nature*. 2006 Dec 14;444(7121):840-6. doi: 10.1038/nature05482. PMID: 17167471.
- 18) Igarashi A, Capucci S, Ota R, Wada S, Schneck V. Impact of weight loss on obesity-related complications and direct healthcare costs in Japan: A modelling study. *Diabetes Obes Metab*. 2025 Jun;27(6):3017-3024. doi: 10.1111/dom.16306. Epub 2025 Mar 20. PMID: 40110596; PMCID: PMC12046468.
- 19) Morton, G. J., Meek, T. H., & Schwartz, M. W. (2014). Neurobiology of food intake. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, 15(6), 367-378.
- 20) Volkow, N. D., Wang, G. J., Tomasi, D., & Baler, R. D. (2013). Obesity and addiction. *Biological Psychiatry*, 73(9), 811-818.
- 21) Rosen, E. D., & Spiegelman, B. M. (2014). What we talk about when we talk about fat. *Cell*, 156(1-2), 20-44.
- 22) Hotamisligil, G. S. (2006). Inflammation and metabolic disorders. *Nature*, 444(7121), 860-867.
- 23) Kadowaki, T., & Yamauchi, T. (2005). Adiponectin and its receptors. *Endocrine Reviews*, 26(3), 439-451.
- 24) Turnbaugh, P. J., Ley, R. E., Mahowald, M. A., et al. (2006). Obesity-associated gut microbiome. *Nature*, 444(7122), 1027-1031.
- 25) Canfora EE, Meex RCR, Venema K, Blaak EE. Gut microbial metabolites in obesity, NAFLD and T2DM. *Nat Rev Endocrinol*. 2019 May;15(5):261-273. doi: 10.1038/s41574-019-0156-z. PMID: 30670819.
- 26) Cani, P. D., Amar, J., Iglesias, M. A., Poggi, M., et al. (2007). Metabolic endotoxemia initiates obesity and insulin resistance. *Diabetes*, 56(7), 1761-1772.
- 27) Monteiro, C. A., Moubarac, J. C., Cannon, G., Ng, S. W., & Popkin, B. (2013). Ultra-processed products dominate. *Obesity Reviews*, 14(S2), 21-28.
- 28) Booth, F. W., Roberts, C. K., & Laye, M. J. (2012). Lack of exercise is a major cause of chronic diseases. *Comprehensive Physiology*, 2(2), 1143-1211.
- 29) Heymsfield, S. B., & Wadden, T. A. (2017). Mechanisms and management of obesity. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 376(3), 254-266.